

Synthesis and fungicidal activities of some 2-substituted arylamino-5-(2'-furyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-c]thiazoles and 5-substituted aryl-2-substituted arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-c]thiazoles

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Abstract : Several 2-substituted arylamino-5-(2'-furyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-c]thiazoles have been synthesised by cyclisation of 3-substituted aryl thiocarbanilido-2-(2'-furyl)thiazolidin-4-ones with conc. H₂SO₄ with constant stirring in cold and 5-substituted aryl-2-substituted arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-c]thiazoles have been synthesised by the cyclisation of 2-substituted aryl-3-substituted arylthiourido-thiazolidin-4-ones with conc. H₂SO₄ with constant stirring in cold and screened for their antifungal activities against *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Cephalosporium sacchari*.

Keywords : 1,3,4-Thiadiazoles[3,2-c]thiazoles, fungicidal activity.

Introduction

1,3,4-Thiadiazole nucleus is associated with broad spectrum of biocidal activities possibly by virtue of the toxophoric >N-C-S moiety^{1,2}. Further 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole may be viewed as cyclic analogue of thiosemicarbazone, the physiological properties^{3,4} of which have been well established. Likewise 1,2,4-triazoles[3,2-c]thiazoles and related compounds have been known to display fungicidal activity⁵.

The above observation coupled with the view that planarity and compactness of a molecule might augment its other biological activities as it does with herbicidal activities⁶, let us to study a molecule which combines these two biolabile rings together to give a compact and planar system. Thus synthesis of 2-substituted aryl amino-5-(2'-furyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-c]thiazoles (4) and 5-substituted aryl-2-substituted aryl amino-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-c]thiazoles (7) was undertaken with a view to getting compounds of better biological activities. The structure of these compounds was established by their IR, ¹H NMR spectral data and elemental analysis.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 881 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer at 60 MHz.

Procedure for one typical case for each step has been described.

Aryl thiosemicarbazide (1a : R = 4-OCH₃) :

4-Methoxyphenylthiosemicarbazide was prepared according to the method of Kazakov *et al.*⁷. A solution of 4-methoxyaniline (12.3 g, 0.1 M) in ammonia (16.0 ml, 0.1 M, d 0.88) was treated with carbon disulphide (9.1 ml) below 30 °C. The whole solution was stirred well till carbon disulphide had completely dissolved. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for overnight and then a solution of sodium chloroacetate (11.7 g) was added followed by hydrazine hydrate (6.0 ml). It was warmed, cooled and filtered. The crystals separated were recrystallised from aq. ethanol (m.p. 152 °C, literature⁸ reports the same m.p.) other arylthiosemicarbazides thus prepared in a similar way.

1-Aryl-4-furylidene-thiosemicarbazones (2a : R = 4-OCH₃) :

It was prepared by the method of Shanker⁹. A mixture of 4-methoxyphenyl thiosemicarbazide (4.2 g, 0.02 M) and furfuraldehyde (1.7 ml, 0.02 M) was refluxed in methanol using gl. CH₃COOH as a catalyst for 3–4 h. The mixture was cooled and poured in to water. The product was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aq. ethanol, m.p. 154 °C.

3-(Arylthiocarbanilido)-2-(2'-furyl)thiazolidin-4-ones (3a : R=4-OCH₃) :

It was prepared by refluxing 1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-furylidene-thiosemicarbazone (3.0 g, 0.01 M) and mercapto acetic acid (0.8 ml, 0.01 M) in dioxane for 3–4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into water and neutralized by NaHCO₃. The solid mass was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from aq. ethanol, m.p. 114 °C; IR (KBr) : 3280 (NH), 1640 (C=O), 1540, 1500, 1460 (C=C aromatic ring), 1270, 1020 (C–O–C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.1 (1H, s, S-CH-N), 3.6 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 3.4 (2H, s, CH₂S), 6.7–7.8 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.0 (1H, s, -NH).

2-(Arylamino)-5-(2'-furyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-c]thiazoles (4a : R = 4-OCH₃) :

The requisite 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)thiocarbanilido-2-(2'-furyl)thiazolidin-4-one (1.7 g, 0.005 M) was treated with conc. H₂SO₄ with constant stirring in cold. When addition is completed the residue was left at room temperature for 4 h and poured into cold water on neutralisation with ammonia, the desired product precipitated out. It was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aq. ethanol, m.p. 132 °C; IR (KBr) : 3240 (-NH), 1600 (C=N), 1500, 1450, 1440 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1230, 1050 (C–S–C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.7 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.8 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.1 (1H, s, CH-S), 6.2–7.6 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.6 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (*m/z*) : 331 (M⁺); (4b : R = H) : m.p. 108 °C; IR (KBr) : 3244 (-NH), 1603 (C=N), 1509, 1450, 1446 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1228, 1050 (C–S–C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 4.8 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.0 (1H, s, CH-S), 6.1–7.8 (8H, m, Ar-H), 8.6 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (*m/z*) : 301 (M⁺); (4c : R = Cl) : m.p. 118 °C; IR (KBr) : 3240 (-NH), 1600 (C=N), 1500, 1450, 1440 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1230, 1050 (C–S–C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-

*d*₆) : δ 4.7 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.2 (1H, s, CH-S), 6.2–7.7 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.8 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (*m/z*) : 335, 337 (M⁺, M⁺²); (4d : R = 4-CH₃) : m.p. 110 °C; IR (KBr) : 3240 (-NH), 1600 (C=N), 1500, 1450, 1440 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1230, 1050 (C–S–C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.8 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.1 (1H, s, CH-S), 6.2–7.5 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.8 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (*m/z*) : 315 (M⁺); (4e : R = 2-CH₃) : m.p. 164 °C; IR (KBr) : 3240 (-NH), 1600 (C=N), 1500, 1450, 1440 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1230, 1050 (C–S–C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.7 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.2 (1H, s, CH-S), 6.2–7.6 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.7 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (*m/z*) : 315 (M⁺).

1-Aryl-4-arylideno-thiosemicarbazones (5a : R = 4-Cl, R' = 2-OH) :

It was prepared according to the method of Sen and Gupta¹⁰ by refluxing 4-chlorophenyl thiosemicarbazide (4.2 g, 0.02 M) and 2-hydroxy benzaldehyde (2.7 g, 0.02 M) in methanol using gl. CH₃COOH as catalyst for 3–4 h. The mixture was cooled and poured in to water, the compound thus precipitated out which was purified by aq. ethanol, m.p. 152 °C.

2-Aryl-3-substituted arylthiourido-thiazolidin-4-ones (6a : R = 4-Cl, R' = 2-OH) :

It was prepared by refluxing 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-4-(2-hydroxybenzylideno)thiosemicarbazone (3.2 g, 0.01 M) and mercapto acetic acid (0.8 ml, 0.01 M) in dioxane for 3–4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled poured into water and neutralized by NaHCO₃. The solid mass was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from aq. ethanol, m.p. 139 °C; IR (KBr) : 3285 (NH), 1650 (C=O), 1530, 1490, 1450 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1260, 1010 (C–O–C) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.2 (1H, s, S-CH-N), 3.7 (3H, s, OH), 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂S), 6.6–7.7 (17H, m, Ar-H), 8.0 (1H, s, -NH).

5-Aryl-2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-c]thiazoles (7a : R = 4-Cl, R' = 2-OH) :

The requisite 2-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-thiourido thiazolidin-4-one (1.8 g, 0.005 M) was treated with conc. H₂SO₄ (A.R., 0.5 ml) with constant stirring in cold. When addition is completed the residue was left at room temperature for 4 h and poured in to cold water. Upon neutralization with ammonia, the product was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aq. ethanol, m.p.

162 °C; IR (KBr) : 3590 (-OH), 3230 (-NH), 1608 (C=N), 1340, 1512, 1456, 1450 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1238, 1052 (C-S-C) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) : δ 4.8 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.0 (1H, s, N-CH-S), 6.7-7.3 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.4 (1H, b, -OH), 10.2 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (m/z) : 361, 363 (M^+ , M^{+2}); (7b : R = 4-Cl, R' = H) : m.p. 147 °C; IR (KBr) : 3233 (-NH), 1600 (C=N), 1343, 1509, 1454, 1450 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1236, 1056 (C-S-C) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) : δ 4.7 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.0 (1H, s, N-CH-S), 6.6-7.3 (8H, m, Ar-H), 10.7 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (m/z) : 345, 347 (M^+ , M^{+2}); (7c : R = 4-Cl, R' = 4-CH₃) : m.p. 142 °C; IR (KBr) : 3240 (-NH), 1600

(C=N), 1348, 1512, 1458, 1448 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1248, 1050 (C-S-C) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) : δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.8 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.1 (1H, s, N-CH-S), 6.6-7.4 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.2 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (m/z) : 359, 361 (M^+ , M^{+2}); (7d : R = 4-Cl, R' = 3-NO₂) : m.p. 169 °C; IR (KBr) : 3240 (-NH), 1602 (C=N), 1560, 1340, 1506, 1460, 1448 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1240, 1052 (C-S-C) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) : δ 4.9 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.2 (1H, s, N-CH-S), 6.6-8.1 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.4 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (m/z) : 390, 392 (M^+ , M^{+2}); (7e : R = 4-CH₃, R' = 4-CH₃) : m.p. 126 °C; IR (KBr) : 3232 (-NH), 1610 (C=N), 1339, 1502, 1459,

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|----------------------------|-----------------------------|------------------------|
| 4a, R = 4-OCH ₃ | 7a, R = 4-Cl, | R' = 2-OH |
| 4b, R = H | 7b, R = 4-Cl, | R' = H |
| 4c, R = 4-Cl | 7c, R = 4-Cl, | R' = 4-CH ₃ |
| 4d, R = 4-CH ₃ | 7d, R = 4-Cl, | R' = 3-NO ₂ |
| 4e, R = 2-CH ₃ | 7e, R = 4-CH ₃ , | R' = 4-CH ₃ |
| | 7f, R = 4-CH ₃ , | R' = 2-OH |
| | 7g, R = 4-CH ₃ , | R' = 3-NO ₂ |

Scheme 1

1445 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1238, 1058 (C-S-C) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) : δ 2.3 (6H, s, CH_3), 4.8 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.0 (1H, s, N-CH-S), 6.3-7.2 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.6 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (m/z) : 339 (M^+); (7f : R = 4- CH_3 , R' = 2-OH) : m.p. 158 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3364 (-OH), 3244 (-NH), 1604 (C=N), 1320, 1510, 1454, 1448 (C=C aromatic ring) and 1240, 1050 (C-S-C) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) : δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.8 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.0 (1H, s, N-CH-S), 6.4-7.1 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.4 (1H, b, -OH), 10.3 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (m/z) : 341 (M^+); (7g : R = 4- CH_3 , R' = 3- NO_2) : m.p. 160 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3230 (-NH), 1604 (C=N), 1570, 1508, 1454, 1448 (C=C aromatic ring), 1340, 1234, 1056 (C-S-C) cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6) : δ 2.3 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.8 (1H, s, CH-S), 5.2 (1H, s, N-CH-S), 6.4-8.2 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.4 (1H, b, -NH); EIMS (m/z) : 370 (M^+).

Other such compounds were also prepared in a similar way and their characterization data are given in Table 1.

Results and discussion

Fungicidal activity :

Compound 4a-e and 7a-g were screened for their antifungal activity against *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Cephalosporium sacchari* by agar growth technique¹¹ at 1000, 100 and 10 ppm concentration. The results were compared with commercial fungicide carbendazim tested under similar conditions. Amongst these, the most active compounds 4a, 4c, 7a, 7c and 7e showed activity comparable (91% at 1000 ppm) to that of reference fungicide carbendazim (98% at 1000 ppm) further investigations of this compound on a wider range of fungi as well as with higher dilution in progress.

Table 1. Characterization data of compounds 4a-e and 7a-g

Compd.	M.p. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Yield (%)	Mol. formula	Analysis (%) :		
				Found	(Calcd.)	
				C	H	N
4a	132	77	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	54.44 (54.22)	4.50 (4.22)	12.85 (12.65)
4b	108	82	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}$	55.63 (55.33)	3.97 (3.89)	13.91 (13.71)
4c	118	79	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{OCl}$	49.93 (49.49)	3.27 (3.57)	12.48 (12.84)
4d	110	74	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}$	56.96 (56.69)	4.43 (4.34)	13.29 (13.79)
4e	164	75	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}$	56.96 (56.80)	4.43 (4.35)	13.29 (13.78)
7a	162	77	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{OCl}$	53.32 (53.11)	3.52 (3.34)	11.82 (11.61)
7b	147	68	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{Cl}$	55.57 (55.75)	3.47 (3.17)	12.15 (12.51)
7c	142	70	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{Cl}$	56.74 (56.47)	3.89 (3.98)	11.68 (11.84)
7d	169	72	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	49.16 (49.60)	2.81 (2.59)	14.34 (14.43)
7e	126	79	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$	63.71 (63.61)	5.01 (5.31)	12.38 (12.79)
7f	158	80	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}$	55.82 (55.62)	4.39 (4.80)	12.31 (12.13)
7g	160	65	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	55.13 (55.01)	3.78 (4.87)	15.13 (15.23)

Note

The detailed data on compounds **4a**, **4c**, **7a**, **7c** and **7e** having promising fungicidal activity are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Fungicidal activity of compounds **4a**, **4c**, **7a**, **7c** and **7e**

Compd.	<i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i>			<i>Cephalosporium sacchari</i>		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
4a	92	47	29	86	46	34
4c	88	46	24	85	42	26
7a	90	43	26	92	44	28
7c	89	53	33	87	41	31
7e	83	32	16	86	39	23
Carbendazim	100	97	85	100	93	80

Conclusion :

We have synthesised 2-substituted arylamino-5-(2'-furyl)-1,3,4-thiazdiazolo[3,2-c]thiazoles and 5-substituted aryl-2-substituted arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-c]thiazoles. All these compounds have been assayed for their fungicidal activities against *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Cephalosporium sacchari*. Some of them have shown excellent fungicidal activity.

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References

1. W. J. Stanley, Ger. Offen., 1977, 2704288 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, **87**, 201546).
2. F. Suzuki, J. Kawakami, S. Yamamoto and Y. Kosai, Japan Kokai, 1977, 7776432 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **88**, 100351).
3. N. Tiwari, B. Chaturvedi and Nizamuddin, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, **28**, 200.
4. B. Chaturvedi, N. Tiwari and Nizamuddin, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, **28**, 358.
5. K. Singh, N. Tiwari and Nizamuddin, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1993, **32**, 1086.
6. N. Tiwari, B. Chaturvedi and Nizamuddin, *J. Pesticide Science Japan*, 1990, **15**, 357.
7. V. Y. Kazakov, I. Y. Postovskii, I. Y. Ucheb and Z. Khim, *Ikhim Technol.*, 1961, **4**, 238 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1961, **55**, 23415).
8. M. Tister, *Chem. Acta*, 1956, **28**, 147 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, **51**, 12016).
9. A. Kumar, M. Verma, M. Bhalla, A. K. Saxena and K. Shanker, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1991, **1**, 129.
10. A. B. Sen and S. K. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 693.
11. S. Giri and Nizamuddin, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1978, **42**, 41.

